

**Appendix for Balbach (2026) “How Does Delegation Affect the
Administrative Capacity of the Hollow State?”**

Appendix A Operationalization of Political Control

The highest degree of political control is found in rank 6, which contains administrative entities that are headed by elected government members. Rank 6 contains organizations such as national or state ministries and municipalities. Constitutionally and in general administrative law, municipalities and their subordinate levels are treated as part of the indirect entities of the state-level administration. This, however, may be misleading to an international audience. Municipalities in Germany have considerable independence from the government and administration of the state that they are located in; this principle is called municipal self-administration (art. 28 par. 2 German Basic Law [the German national constitution]). Mayors are more than managers of municipalities and implementers of state legislation; they are political leaders (compare Swedish municipalities in Lindström et al., 2022). Therefore, the present study regards municipalities as being as politically controlled as state ministries and national ministries are. They are not as shielded as subordinate indirect entities of a state are.

Rank 5 contains entities that are headed by unelected officials. These officials are always overseen by an entity with an elected government head. Entities in rank 5 are considered to be part of the classical public administration apparatus, while the following entities in rank 4 are not. Structures of the federal and state administration in Germany categorize entities by whether they are a legal person, namely, as direct and indirect entities (Bogumil, 2007; Bogumil & Jann, 2020). Depending on whether an organization is a legal person, it can or cannot be sued, be an owner of organizational assets, or be party to a contract (Reimer, 2018). The direct entities are further subdivided into uppermost, upper, middle, and lower entities. These structural patterns (direct-indirect; uppermost to lower) are mirrored between the national and the state levels, with each state having its own constitution expressing those patterns.

A subset of rank 5 has been studied before by Bach and Jann (2010). In their study of organizational autonomy in the German federal (national) public sector, Bach and Jann (2010) distinguish four types of federal non-ministerial administration (p. 448): direct administration, indirect administration, private law administration and charged administration. Direct versus indirect oversight differs by whether they face oversight and intervention in legal or also operational matters. The present study subsumes them within rank 5. Private law administration and charged administration fall under private law are part of rank 1.

Rank 4 contains corporations whose heads are, naturally, unelected officials. They pursue public sector goals while practicing accounting practices akin to the private sector. Their formal oversight entity is usually from rank 5 with an unelected government member as head. Examples of rank 4 entities are social security institutions or public universities. Rank 3 contains public law institutions (in German: “Anstalten”) such as the German Federal Bank, public television channels, public transportation cooperations between counties, and local public banks. Their heads are unelected, while government and parliament members sit on the board. Rank 2 contains public law foundations such as the Foundation German Historical Museum. The heads of these foundations are unelected. Elected government members are members of boards of trustees. Rank 1 contains private law organizations under the dominant influence of public authorities such as Deutsche Bahn (the federal-state-owned train company) or defense firms where the federal state owns shares. Unelected officials of categories 6 or 5 are board members.

This yields the following spectrum of political control, from lowest to highest: (1) Private law organization influenced by public authorities at the federal, state, or municipal level. (2) Public law foundation at the federal, state, or municipal level. (3) Public law institution at the federal, state, or municipal level. (4) Public law corporation at the federal,

state, or municipal level. (5) Upper, middle, or lower federal authority; upper, middle, or lower state authority. (6) Highest federal authority; highest state authority; municipal authority.

The entity types within political control regimes are legally defined in German law. Therefore, they are listed here in the German language:

1. Privatrechtliche Organisation, auf die die öffentliche Hand beherrschenden Einfluss ausübt, auf der Bundes-, Landes- oder Kommunalebene
2. Stiftung des öffentlichen Rechts auf Bundes-, Landes- oder Kommunalebene
3. Anstalt des öffentlichen Rechts auf Bundes-, Landes- oder Kommunalebene
4. Körperschaft des öffentlichen Rechts auf Bundes-, Landes- oder Kommunalebene
5. Obere, mittlere oder untere Bundesbehörde; Obere, mittlere oder untere Landesbehörde
6. Oberste Bundesbehörde; Oberste Landesbehörde; Kommunalbehörde

Appendix B Overview of Variables

Appendix Table 1 Focal Variables

Concept	Variable type	Measurement	Implementation	Reference
Asset specificity	Independent variable, ratio	Asset specificity scores	Three leading digits of Common Procurement Vocabulary code Match digits and assign asset specificity score	Potoski et al. (2025)
Measurement difficulty	Independent variable, ratio	Ease of measurement scores	Three leading digits of Common Procurement Vocabulary code Match digits and assign asset specificity score	Potoski et al. (2025)
Transaction frequency	Independent variable, dummy	One versus several instances of contract object can be procured by contracting authority (Geyskens et al., 2006, p. 532)	Is it framework contract? No (reference category)/Yes.	(Casady et al., 2023; Petersen et al., 2022)

Political control	Independent variable, ordinal	Ranking of degree of exposure to political influence by public sector organization type	For each legal type of the buyer, assign ordinal score based on ranking of political control regime	Political steering (Bach & Jann, 2010; Maggetti & Verhoest, 2014) External uncertainty (Bozeman, 1987; Donahue & Nye, 2002; Mayer, 2009)
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Appendix Table 2 Control Variables

Level	Concept	Variable type	Measurement	Reference
Contract level	Competition	Count	Number of bidders	(Petersen et al., 2022)
Contract level	Competition	Ratio	Contract duration	(Petersen et al., 2022)
Contract level	Competition	Count	Number of lots	(Casady et al., 2023; Lund-Sørensen et al., 2022)
Contract level	Discretion	Ratio	Weighting of price and quality If lowest price award criteria, then 100% If EMAT award criteria, then between 0-100%	(Casady et al., 2023; Lund-Sørensen et al., 2022)
Contract level	Year	Factor	Year of the reported cross-section	

Appendix C Additional Descriptives

Appendix Table 3 Additional Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Stats / Values	Freqs (% of Valid)	Graph	Valid	Missing
federal_state [factor]	1. Schleswig-Holstein 2. Hamburg 3. Lower Saxony 4. Bremen 5. North Rhine-Westphalia 6. Hesse 7. Rhineland-Palatinate 8. Baden-Württemberg 9. Bavaria 10. Saarland 11. Berlin 12. Brandenburg 13. Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania 14. Saxony 15. Saxony-Anhalt 16. Thuringia 17. 99	14954 (2.8%) 12823 (2.4%) 54196 (10.1%) 4431 (0.8%) 103047 (19.1%) 43451 (8.1%) 27198 (5.1%) 60893 (11.3%) 84188 (15.6%) 5071 (0.9%) 29685 (5.5%) 23456 (4.4%) 16968 (3.2%) 29468 (5.5%) 15736 (2.9%) 12554 (2.3%) 0 (0.0%)		538119 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)
gov_levels [character]	1. federal 2. municipal 3. other 4. state	58140 (10.8%) 278358 (51.7%) 42438 (7.9%) 159183 (29.6%)		538119 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)
contract_type [factor]	1. Public contract by a public contracting authority above the EU threshold (n 2. Public contract for social or other specific services by a public contracti 3. Public contract by a sectoral contracting authority (notification under § 3 4. Public contract for social or other specific services by a sectoral contrac 5. Concession by a concession grantor (notification under § 3 Abs. 1 Nr. 5 Ver 6. Concession for social or other specific services by a concession grantor (n 7. Defense or security-specific public contract by a public contracting author 8. Public contract by a public contracting authority below the EU threshold (n	45125 (8.4%) 882 (0.2%) 1473 (0.3%) 0 (0.0%) 0 (0.0%) 0 (0.0%) 346 (0.1%) 490293 (91.1%)		538119 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)
organization_type [factor]	1. Fed Supreme Authority 2. Fed Up/Mid/Low Authority 3. Fed Corporation 4. Fed Institution 5. Fed Foundation 6. Fed Other 7. State Supreme Authority 8. State Up/Mid/Low Authority 9. State Corporation 10. State Institution 11. State Foundation 12. State Other 13. Mun Authority 14. Mun Corporation 15. Mun Institution 16. Mun Foundation 17. Mun Other 18. Remaining Other	6750 (1.3%) 17581 (3.3%) 6330 (1.2%) 3679 (0.7%) 3056 (0.6%) 20744 (3.9%) 9571 (1.8%) 69799 (13.0%) 28792 (5.4%) 17208 (3.2%) 3454 (0.6%) 30359 (5.6%) 229323 (42.6%) 30082 (5.6%) 4747 (0.9%) 337 (0.1%) 13869 (2.6%) 42438 (7.9%)		538119 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)
procedure_type [factor]	1. Public tender (§ 9 UVgO; § 3 Abs. 1 VOB/A) 2. Restricted tender with participation competition (§ 10 UVgO; § 3 Abs. 2 VOB 3. Restricted tender without participation competition (§ 11 UVgO; § 3 Abs. 2 4. Negotiated award / open award with participation competition (§ 12 Abs. 1 U 5. Negotiated award / open award without participation competition (§ 12 Abs. 6. Other procedures 7. Open procedure (§ 15 VgV; § 3 EU Nr. 1 VOB/A) 8. Restricted procedure (§ 16 VgV; § 3 EU Nr. 2 VOB/A) 9. Negotiated procedure with participation competition (§ 17 Abs. 1 VgV; § 3 E 10. Negotiated procedure without participation competition (§ 17 Abs. 5 VgV; § 11. Competitive dialogue (§ 18 VgV; § 3 EU Nr. 4 VOB/A) 12. Innovation partnership (§ 19 VgV; § 3 EU Nr. 5 VOB/A) 13. Open procedure (§ 15 VgV) 14. Restricted procedure (§ 16 VgV) 15. Negotiated procedure with participation competition (§ 17 Abs. 1 VgV) 16. Negotiated procedure without participation competition (§ 17 Abs. 5 VgV) 17. Innovation partnership (§ 19 VgV) 18. Open procedure (§ 14 SektVO) [12 others]	181847 (33.8%) 5278 (1.0%) 96508 (17.9%) 6470 (1.2%) 146263 (27.2%) 38653 (7.2%) 41950 (7.8%) 1349 (0.3%) 6417 (1.2%) 7931 (1.5%) 36 (0.0%) 4 (0.0%) 920 (0.2%) 10 (0.0%) 23 (0.0%) 142 (0.0%) 2 (0.0%) 551 (0.1%) 3765 (0.7%)		538119 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)

Variable	Stats / Values	Freqs (% of Valid)	Graph	Valid	Missing
contract_value [numeric]	Mean (sd) : 166436.7 (220118.2) min ≤ med ≤ max: 1001 ≤ 79069 ≤ 1328556 IQR (CV) : 144736 (1.3)	241411 distinct values		538119 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)
country_of_origin [character]	1. DE 2. (Empty string) 3. 99 4. AT 5. US 6. NL 7. CH 8. GB 9. FR 10. BE 11. SE 12. CA 13. IT 14. DK 15. PL 16. ES 17. IE 18. FI [107 others]	356315 (66.2%) 103710 (19.3%) 70116 (13.0%) 1261 (0.2%) 999 (0.2%) 830 (0.2%) 786 (0.1%) 671 (0.1%) 666 (0.1%) 250 (0.0%) 203 (0.0%) 198 (0.0%) 197 (0.0%) 189 (0.0%) 167 (0.0%) 160 (0.0%) 104 (0.0%) 92 (0.0%) 1205 (0.2%)		538119 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)
product_type [factor]	1. Construction contract 2. Supply contract 3. Service contract 4. Contracts for social or other specific services	265121 (49.3%) 120997 (22.5%) 151120 (28.1%) 881 (0.2%)		538119 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)
product_name [character]	1. Works for complete or part construction and civil engineering work 2. Tradesman services 3. Engineering and architect consultancy 4. Other construction work 5. Site preparation work 6. Motor vehicles 7. IT consultancy and program development 8. Building and construction material 9. Other Laboratory, optical and precision equipment (excl. glasses) 10. Computers and tablets 11. Cleaning and sanitation services 12. Furniture and fixtures - office and school furniture 13. Other software package and information systems 14. Medical equipment 15. Maintenance of green areas, sports facilities, etc. 16. Miscellaneous transport equipment and spare parts 17. Forestry services 18. Instruments for checking physical characteristics [142 others]	100159 (19.7%) 86485 (17.0%) 53881 (10.6%) 33962 (6.7%) 21246 (4.2%) 13366 (2.6%) 12574 (2.5%) 9012 (1.8%) 8412 (1.7%) 7901 (1.6%) 7143 (1.4%) 6893 (1.4%) 6218 (1.2%) 5861 (1.2%) 4652 (0.9%) 4475 (0.9%) 3633 (0.7%) 3335 (0.7%) 120139 (23.6%)		509347 (94.7%)	28772 (5.3%)

Appendix D Missing Values Analysis

The reporting per procurement procedure is largely automated, which may lead to systematic reporting patterns in the data that become visible in the patterns of missing values. This is why matrix plots and analysis using the index of local sensitivity to nonignorability (ISNI) were used to determine whether the focal outcome and explanatory variables in the model are missing at random (MAR), which was confirmed.

The t-test of differences in asset specificity, comparing group with missing values versus group without missing values for environmental sustainability, did not find a significant difference.

welch Two Sample t-test

```
data:  mis_GC and obs_GC
t = -2.7027, df = 12234, p-value = 0.006887
alternative hypothesis: true difference in means is not equal to 0
95 percent confidence interval:
 -0.010024489 -0.001596437
sample estimates:
mean of x mean of y
 2.347217  2.353027
```

Appendix Figure 1 Differences in asset specificity by whether environmental sustainability value is missing

Appendix Figure 2 Margin plot for environmental sustainability and asset specificity

Appendix Figure 3 Aggregation Plot for Focal Variables

Appendix Figure 4 Matrix Plot

Legend: columns 1-7 are asset specificity, political control, framework agreement, total bids, EU bids, contract lots, federal state, where red means 'missing'

Little's Test

The data is not missing completely at random, it is not MCAR.

```
> #Little's test for normal distributed variables
# A tibble: 1 × 4
  statistic    df p.value missing.patterns
  <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <int>
1 174851. 1150 0 98
```

ISNI Analysis

The data is Missing At Random (MAR).

ISNI Analysis

```
> #ISNI for logistic regression model (sensitivity analysis)
> ymodel <- environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity + measurability +
+           political_control + framework_agreement +
+           discretion + total_bids + eu_bids +
+           contract_lots
> sos.isni<-isni::isniglm(ymodel, family="binomial", data=df_for_MICE)
```

Note: There are missing values in fixed-effect outcome predictors-- asset_specificity measurability framework_agreement discretion total_bids eu_bids contract_lots. Observations with missing values in these predictors will be dropped out from computing ISNI,

which may reduce ISNI values if the outcome is missing concurrently. Alternatively one can impute these missing predictors values and re-compute ISNI. # weights: 10 (9 variable)

```
initial value 168619.835174
```

```
iter 10 value 46085.566547
```

```
final value 42773.613682
```

```
converged
```

```
> summary(sos.isni)
```

call:

```
isni::isniglmm(formula = ymodel, family = "binomial", data = df_for_MICE)
```

	MAR Est.	Std. Err	ISNI	c
(Intercept)	-0.0958577	0.0948049	0.07078991	1.3392
asset_specificity	-1.0330847	0.0405534	-0.02726947	1.4871
measurability	-0.0926890	0.0231500	-0.00641538	3.6085
political_control	0.0055770	0.0039638	-0.00114528	3.4610
framework_agreement	0.1601925	0.0278783	0.02552776	1.0921
discretion	0.1935094	0.0091744	0.03607742	0.2543
total_bids	0.0047681	0.0012239	0.00089715	1.3642
eu_bids	-0.0725683	0.0093917	0.01334692	0.7037
contract_lots	-0.0308616	0.0268803	0.04575571	0.5875

Appendix E Imputation

The missing values analysis confirmed that the data was missing at random (MAR). Therefore, multiple imputation by chained equations (MICE) was suitable, regardless of the share of missings (Madley-Dowd et al., 2019). The algorithm performed 50 multiple imputations using predictive mean matching (PMM) over 5 iterations. Appendix Figure 5 shows that the means and standard deviations of the focal variables converged over iterations, moving horizontally. This indicates that the imputations were unbiased. Also, the imputed values are plausible, mirroring patterns of prior non-imputed values (cf. magenta imputations versus blue non-imputations).

Appendix Figure 5 Mean and standard deviation over 5 iterations per variable

Appendix Figure 6 Imputed (magenta) versus Non-Imputed Values

Appendix F Details on Logistic GLMM with Random Intercept by

Location

Using standardized predictors for AMEs with intuitive sizes, asset specificity continues to have the largest effect.

	Term	Contrast	Estimate	Std. Error	z	Pr(> z)	S	2.5 %	97.5 %
	asset_specificity_std	dy/dx	-0.01994	0.002916	-6.84	< 0.001	36.8	-0.025655	-0.01422
	contract_lots	1 - 0	-0.01010	0.002010	-5.02	< 0.001	20.9	-0.014041	-0.00616
	discretion_std	dy/dx	0.01133	0.001679	6.75	< 0.001	35.9	0.008039	0.01462
	eu_bids_std	dy/dx	-0.00595	0.001026	-5.80	< 0.001	27.1	-0.007957	-0.00394
	framework_agreement	1 - 0	0.01469	0.002589	5.67	< 0.001	26.1	0.009611	0.01976
	measurability_std	dy/dx	0.00181	0.000490	3.69	< 0.001	12.1	0.000847	0.00277
	political_control	dy/dx	0.00612	0.000913	6.71	< 0.001	35.6	0.004334	0.00791
	total_bids_std	dy/dx	0.00216	0.000475	4.54	< 0.001	17.5	0.001227	0.00309
	year	2022 - 2021	-0.00313	0.001041	-3.01	0.00264	8.6	-0.005169	-0.00109
	year	2023 - 2021	0.00679	0.001363	4.99	< 0.001	20.6	0.004123	0.00946

Type: response

In what follows, the coefficients in log-odds are presented.

```

Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Adaptive Gauss-Hermite Quadrature, nAGQ = 0) ['glmerMod']
Family: binomial ( logit )
Formula: environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity + measurability
+ framework_agreement + political_control + discretion + total_bids +
eu_bids + contract_lots + (1 | federal_state) + year
Data: df_imp_15
Control: glmerControl(optimizer = "bobyqa")

```

AIC	BIC	logLik	deviance	df.resid
307992.5	308126.9	-153984.3	307968.5	538107

Scaled residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-50.694	-0.341	-0.269	-0.205	26.871

Random effects:

Groups	Name	Variance	Std.Dev.
federal_state	(Intercept)	0.5841	0.7643

Number of obs: 538119, groups: federal_state, 16

Fixed effects:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
(Intercept)	-0.6047162	0.2009967	-3.009	0.002625 **
asset_specificity	-1.2089629	0.0259950	-46.507	< 0.0000000000000000002 ***
measurability	0.0648480	0.0148681	4.362	0.000012913493839 ***
framework_agreement	0.1754112	0.0173348	10.119	< 0.0000000000000000002 ***
political_control	0.0773268	0.0027541	28.077	< 0.0000000000000000002 ***
discretion	0.1906450	0.0061345	31.078	< 0.0000000000000000002 ***

```

total_bids      0.0041122  0.0006817   6.032   0.000000001619572 ***
eu_bids        -0.0657754  0.0061936  -10.620 < 0.00000000000000002 ***
contract_lots  -0.1330693  0.0187036   -7.115   0.000000000001122 ***
year2022       -0.0406272  0.0121388   -3.347   0.000817 ***
year2023       0.0841227  0.0117763    7.143   0.000000000000911 ***

```

```

---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

Correlation of Fixed Effects:

```

(Intr) asst_s msrblt frmwr_ pltcl_ dscrtn ttl_bd eu_bds cntrc_
yr2022
asst_spcfct -0.222
measurablt  -0.097 -0.368
frmwrk_grmn -0.007 -0.076  0.116
pltcl_cntrl -0.078  0.063 -0.024  0.051
discretion  -0.008 -0.112 -0.020 -0.087  0.087
total_bids  -0.019  0.028  0.010  0.003 -0.043  0.001
eu_bids     -0.008  0.016 -0.002  0.002  0.026 -0.028 -0.048
contract_lts -0.029  0.005  0.129 -0.079 -0.019 -0.096 -0.102 -0.034
year2022    -0.031  0.002  0.001 -0.016 -0.004 -0.004  0.022  0.003 -0.003
year2023    -0.031  0.000  0.000 -0.012  0.004 -0.004  0.008  0.000 -0.004
0.516

```

The empty model had an AIC of 327577.8, adding the random intercept by location (federal state) improved the AIC to 312260. Adding the fixed effects gives an AIC of 307992.5 – this is the model presented in the manuscript. Adding a random slope – which is not justified by the theoretical framework – would yield an AIC of 307793.8. By comparison, including a random intercept by organization type gives a higher AIC value of 312310.7.

The assumptions underlying the logistic GLMM were confirmed by the following checks. Among the predictors, there is no multicollinearity, as the Pearson correlation coefficient for the focal variables shows.

Appendix Figure 7 Pearson Correlations

The GLMM with a random intercept better fits the data, having lower AIC and BIC values and being theoretically justified, while random slopes are not theoretically justified nor lower AIC and BIC substantively.

The partial residuals plot shows whether the relationship between each predictor and the binary outcome is linear while adjusting for all other predictors and random effects. If the linearity assumption holds, the resulting plot should show a roughly straight-line pattern. The conditional expectation is shown as a line that is the predicted relationship between the predictor and the response. The partial residuals are overlaid as points, showing the actual data adjusted for other variables. Largely, the residuals follow a linear trend. There is no clear trend of heteroscedasticity, while the residuals of lower asset specificity do seem to spread wider.

Appendix Figure 8 Partial Residuals Plots

The data had been cleaned; impossible values were removed. Contracts with contract values above the 95th percentile were excluded. The sample is the population, it is all public procurement procedures in Germany from 2021-2023. Since the data reflect the population distribution, with a sample size of $N=566,442$ and bounded predictor values, it is very unlikely that outliers are influential on estimates. Lastly, I am not aware of a package in R that can calculate Cook's distance for a logistic GLMM with a random intercept.

Appendix Figure 9 Fitted Versus Residuals Plot

Appendix G Separate Estimations by Federal State

Appendix Figure 10 Average Marginal Effect by Location of Buyer Organization


```
> # Print the summary of each model
> lapply(logit_model_split, summary)
$`Schleswig-Holstein`
```

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
     measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
     discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
     family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	-0.735578	0.467178	-1.575	0.11537	
asset_specificity	-1.967596	0.202836	-9.700	< 0.0000000000000002	***
measurability	0.236127	0.110001	2.147	0.03183	*
political_control	0.233338	0.025961	8.988	< 0.0000000000000002	***
framework_agreement	0.553290	0.122988	4.499	0.00000683569083	***
discretion	0.304737	0.043591	6.991	0.000000000000273	***
total_bids	0.005002	0.008599	0.582	0.56080	
eu_bids	-0.064346	0.053200	-1.210	0.22647	
contract_lots	-0.275849	0.135207	-2.040	0.04133	*
year2022	0.306951	0.093900	3.269	0.00108	**
year2023	0.215492	0.094383	2.283	0.02242	*

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 6298.7 on 14953 degrees of freedom
 Residual deviance: 6029.1 on 14943 degrees of freedom
 AIC: 6051.1

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 6

`$Hamburg`

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
     measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
     discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
     family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	0.660377	0.386154	1.710	0.08724	.
asset_specificity	-2.089292	0.165961	-12.589	< 0.0000000000000002	***
measurability	0.520807	0.097098	5.364	0.000000081532642	***
political_control	0.190570	0.019403	9.822	< 0.0000000000000002	***
framework_agreement	0.339861	0.105513	3.221	0.00128	**
discretion	0.008822	0.035203	0.251	0.80212	
total_bids	0.046150	0.007397	6.239	0.000000000440169	***
eu_bids	-0.268003	0.050016	-5.358	0.000000083983758	***
contract_lots	0.643441	0.113783	5.655	0.000000015587469	***
year2022	-0.476545	0.072059	-6.613	0.000000000037587	***
year2023	-0.520027	0.072512	-7.172	0.000000000000741	***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

```
Null deviance: 8501.5 on 12822 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 7973.2 on 12812 degrees of freedom
AIC: 7995.2
```

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 6

`$`Lower Saxony``

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
```

```

measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)

```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	0.541565	0.263264	2.057	0.03968	*
asset_specificity	-0.778291	0.111556	-6.977	0.000000000000302	***
measurability	-0.602589	0.061889	-9.737	< 0.000000000000002	***
political_control	-0.070176	0.012085	-5.807	0.00000000636981	***
framework_agreement	0.494638	0.070672	6.999	0.00000000000258	***
discretion	0.246459	0.027601	8.929	< 0.000000000000002	***
total_bids	-0.012646	0.007406	-1.708	0.08771	.
eu_bids	-0.077869	0.031056	-2.507	0.01216	*
contract_lots	0.237499	0.074606	3.183	0.00146	**
year2022	-0.156225	0.050942	-3.067	0.00216	**
year2023	-0.294792	0.051999	-5.669	0.00000001434737	***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

```

Null deviance: 19290 on 54195 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 18847 on 54185 degrees of freedom
AIC: 18869

```

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 6

\$Bremen

Call:

```

glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)

```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	3.34044	1.35765	2.460	0.013876	*
asset_specificity	-2.53238	0.56929	-4.448	0.00000865	***
measurability	-0.65393	0.33673	-1.942	0.052136	.
political_control	-0.08758	0.06586	-1.330	0.183587	
framework_agreement	1.11750	0.31731	3.522	0.000429	***
discretion	0.45315	0.13064	3.469	0.000523	***
total_bids	-0.05949	0.04606	-1.292	0.196519	
eu_bids	0.07570	0.18333	0.413	0.679653	
contract_lots	-0.90044	0.74511	-1.208	0.226872	
year2022	-0.15656	0.30983	-0.505	0.613329	
year2023	0.67154	0.26048	2.578	0.009935	**

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 879.54 on 4430 degrees of freedom

Residual deviance: 803.00 on 4420 degrees of freedom

AIC: 825

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 7

\$`North Rhine-westphalia`

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
    measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
    discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
    family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	-0.9926407	0.1344272	-7.384	0.0000000000000153	***
asset_specificity	-0.8466374	0.0566349	-14.949	< 0.0000000000000002	***

```

measurability      -0.0952736  0.0325686  -2.925          0.00344 **
political_control  0.1452869  0.0063810  22.769 < 0.0000000000000002 ***
framework_agreement 0.1020154  0.0395332   2.580          0.00987 **
discretion         0.2116747  0.0137971  15.342 < 0.0000000000000002 ***
total_bids         0.0004727  0.0013302   0.355          0.72230
eu_bids            -0.0528854  0.0121633  -4.348         0.000013741720526 ***
contract_lots      0.0640948  0.0375113   1.709          0.08751 .
year2022           -0.1415584  0.0274852  -5.150         0.000000260012411 ***
year2023           -0.0144791  0.0262893  -0.551         0.58180

```

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 62193 on 103046 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 61082 on 103036 degrees of freedom
AIC: 61104

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 5

\$Hesse

Call:

```

glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
     measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
     discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
     family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)

```

Coefficients:

```

              Estimate Std. Error z value      Pr(>|z|)
(Intercept)    3.357117   0.236313  14.206 < 0.0000000000000002 ***
asset_specificity -1.648469   0.102037 -16.156 < 0.0000000000000002 ***
measurability  -0.202172   0.056308  -3.590     0.00033 ***
political_control -0.473613   0.009826 -48.198 < 0.0000000000000002 ***
framework_agreement 0.441822   0.069823   6.328     0.000000000249 ***
discretion     -0.039429   0.021047  -1.873     0.06102 .

```

total_bids	0.024971	0.005994	4.166	0.000030994243	***
eu_bids	-0.141336	0.030591	-4.620	0.000003833415	***
contract_lots	-0.458428	0.087647	-5.230	0.000000169124	***
year2022	-0.026332	0.048977	-0.538	0.59083	
year2023	0.261154	0.047210	5.532	0.000000031706	***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 22563 on 43450 degrees of freedom
 Residual deviance: 19454 on 43440 degrees of freedom
 AIC: 19476

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 6

\$`Rhineland-Palatinate`

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
     measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
     discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
     family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	-1.382484	0.489665	-2.823	0.00475	**
asset_specificity	-1.016777	0.201731	-5.040	0.000000464897477597	***
measurability	0.066189	0.113913	0.581	0.56121	
political_control	-0.063131	0.021743	-2.904	0.00369	**
framework_agreement	0.067683	0.153082	0.442	0.65839	
discretion	0.370209	0.045148	8.200	0.0000000000000000241	***
total_bids	0.007576	0.005873	1.290	0.19700	
eu_bids	-0.010148	0.045449	-0.223	0.82331	
contract_lots	-0.561558	0.120966	-4.642	0.000003445873537163	***
year2022	0.023003	0.086961	0.265	0.79138	

```
year2023          -0.090635  0.088608  -1.023          0.30636
```

```
---
```

```
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)
```

```
Null deviance: 7295.1 on 27197 degrees of freedom
```

```
Residual deviance: 7178.0 on 27187 degrees of freedom
```

```
AIC: 7200
```

```
Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 6
```

```
$`Baden-württemberg`
```

```
Call:
```

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
    measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
    discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
    family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

```
Coefficients:
```

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	-0.805083	0.224378	-3.588	0.000333	***
asset_specificity	-0.865305	0.095546	-9.056	< 0.0000000000000002	***
measurability	-0.502815	0.052691	-9.543	< 0.0000000000000002	***
political_control	0.163114	0.010365	15.737	< 0.0000000000000002	***
framework_agreement	0.404681	0.068003	5.951	0.00000000267	***
discretion	0.408417	0.020022	20.398	< 0.0000000000000002	***
total_bids	0.002812	0.001265	2.224	0.026176	*
eu_bids	-0.201634	0.044605	-4.520	0.00000617210	***
contract_lots	0.006005	0.067340	0.089	0.928942	
year2022	0.054314	0.044477	1.221	0.222018	
year2023	0.162624	0.042778	3.802	0.000144	***

```
---
```

```
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 26806 on 60892 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 25848 on 60882 degrees of freedom
AIC: 25870

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 6

\$Bavaria

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
    measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
    discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
    family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	-1.711348	0.152194	-11.245	< 0.0000000000000002	***
asset_specificity	-1.150749	0.059308	-19.403	< 0.0000000000000002	***
measurability	0.189837	0.034515	5.500	0.00000003795657843	***
political_control	0.292584	0.009131	32.043	< 0.0000000000000002	***
framework_agreement	0.129396	0.046795	2.765	0.00569	**
discretion	0.227873	0.014195	16.053	< 0.0000000000000002	***
total_bids	0.012022	0.002841	4.231	0.00002327317497448	***
eu_bids	-0.078547	0.010659	-7.369	0.00000000000017160	***
contract_lots	-0.380316	0.048554	-7.833	0.00000000000000477	***
year2022	-0.058299	0.027420	-2.126	0.03349	*
year2023	0.085757	0.026702	3.212	0.00132	**

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 60077 on 84187 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 57910 on 84177 degrees of freedom

AIC: 57932

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 5

\$Saarland

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
    measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
    discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
    family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	1.84404	1.18730	1.553	0.12039	
asset_specificity	-1.67783	0.52248	-3.211	0.00132	**
measurability	-0.93210	0.29203	-3.192	0.00141	**
political_control	-0.05583	0.06442	-0.867	0.38615	
framework_agreement	0.76030	0.30505	2.492	0.01269	*
discretion	0.48526	0.11427	4.247	0.0000217	***
total_bids	0.07593	0.02827	2.686	0.00724	**
eu_bids	-0.02320	0.19797	-0.117	0.90671	
contract_lots	0.06989	0.30640	0.228	0.81958	
year2022	0.41711	0.22732	1.835	0.06652	.
year2023	-0.55758	0.28499	-1.957	0.05040	.

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 1037.44 on 5070 degrees of freedom

Residual deviance: 952.45 on 5060 degrees of freedom

AIC: 974.45

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 7

\$Berlin

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
    measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
    discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
    family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	1.657307	0.188074	8.812	< 0.0000000000000002	***
asset_specificity	-1.901066	0.078952	-24.079	< 0.0000000000000002	***
measurability	0.301105	0.043371	6.943	0.000000000000385	***
political_control	0.102206	0.007584	13.477	< 0.0000000000000002	***
framework_agreement	0.137466	0.039652	3.467	0.000527	***
discretion	-0.100883	0.020042	-5.034	0.00000048121045	***
total_bids	0.055603	0.003736	14.883	< 0.0000000000000002	***
eu_bids	-0.064018	0.015813	-4.048	0.00005156016851	***
contract_lots	-0.627002	0.062566	-10.021	< 0.0000000000000002	***
year2022	0.204480	0.038547	5.305	0.00000011282837	***
year2023	0.576703	0.035760	16.127	< 0.0000000000000002	***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 30643 on 29684 degrees of freedom
 Residual deviance: 29072 on 29674 degrees of freedom
 AIC: 29094

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 4

\$Brandenburg

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
    measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
    discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
    family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	-1.426374	0.311420	-4.580	0.000004644803026	***
asset_specificity	-0.178347	0.139483	-1.279	0.201026	
measurability	-0.567053	0.076698	-7.393	0.000000000000143	***
political_control	-0.006581	0.013288	-0.495	0.620436	
framework_agreement	0.192788	0.089236	2.160	0.030739	*
discretion	0.449323	0.026289	17.092	< 0.000000000000002	***
total_bids	-0.010973	0.006729	-1.631	0.102931	
eu_bids	-0.238469	0.049577	-4.810	0.000001508699518	***
contract_lots	0.383726	0.075365	5.092	0.000000355166192	***
year2022	0.250137	0.066916	3.738	0.000185	***
year2023	0.242889	0.066363	3.660	0.000252	***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 11811 on 23455 degrees of freedom
 Residual deviance: 11368 on 23445 degrees of freedom
 AIC: 11390

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 6

\$`Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania`

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
    measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
    discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
    family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	0.055692	0.300403	0.185	0.852922	
asset_specificity	-1.573150	0.129238	-12.173	< 0.0000000000000002	***
measurability	0.334699	0.070130	4.773	0.000001819	***
political_control	0.244630	0.012954	18.884	< 0.0000000000000002	***
framework_agreement	0.275640	0.079439	3.470	0.000521	***
discretion	-0.175363	0.034936	-5.020	0.000000518	***
total_bids	0.021193	0.006369	3.328	0.000876	***
eu_bids	0.010263	0.034503	0.297	0.766124	
contract_lots	-0.147221	0.079800	-1.845	0.065056	.
year2022	0.070376	0.053779	1.309	0.190664	
year2023	0.012197	0.053920	0.226	0.821039	

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 14561 on 16967 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 13885 on 16957 degrees of freedom
AIC: 13907

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 5

\$Saxony

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
    measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
    discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
    family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	-1.252659	0.204732	-6.119	0.000000000944	***

asset_specificity	-1.249184	0.083670	-14.930	<	0.0000000000000002	***
measurability	0.807016	0.051419	15.695	<	0.0000000000000002	***
political_control	0.107928	0.009132	11.819	<	0.0000000000000002	***
framework_agreement	0.234411	0.054631	4.291		0.000017805472	***
discretion	0.091502	0.021857	4.186		0.000028343445	***
total_bids	0.004061	0.003844	1.056		0.2908	
eu_bids	-0.015171	0.049990	-0.303		0.7615	
contract_lots	-0.655829	0.073884	-8.876	<	0.0000000000000002	***
year2022	-0.194134	0.035518	-5.466		0.000000046086	***
year2023	-0.074153	0.035909	-2.065		0.0389	*

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 29888 on 29467 degrees of freedom
 Residual deviance: 29176 on 29457 degrees of freedom
 AIC: 29198

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 4

\$`Saxony-Anhalt`

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
  measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
  discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
  family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	-0.27749	0.49490	-0.561	0.57500	
asset_specificity	-1.31300	0.22125	-5.934	0.00000000295	***
measurability	-0.15568	0.12132	-1.283	0.19941	
political_control	-0.03332	0.02028	-1.643	0.10033	
framework_agreement	0.23008	0.14612	1.575	0.11535	

discretion	0.66781	0.04309	15.499	< 0.0000000000000002	***
total_bids	-0.08275	0.01818	-4.551	0.00000533582	***
eu_bids	0.15838	0.05967	2.654	0.00795	**
contract_lots	0.26849	0.13049	2.058	0.03962	*
year2022	-0.15819	0.10274	-1.540	0.12366	
year2023	0.13117	0.09693	1.353	0.17599	

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 5390.3 on 15735 degrees of freedom
 Residual deviance: 5092.9 on 15725 degrees of freedom
 AIC: 5114.9

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 6

\$Thuringia

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
  measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
  discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
  family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	-2.7424673	0.4978290	-5.509	0.0000000361	***
asset_specificity	-0.0975508	0.2225790	-0.438	0.661187	
measurability	-0.5003104	0.1312992	-3.810	0.000139	***
political_control	0.0990174	0.0246114	4.023	0.0000574036	***
framework_agreement	0.2222649	0.1450397	1.532	0.125413	
discretion	0.4373826	0.0482250	9.070	< 0.0000000000000002	***
total_bids	0.0006423	0.0038685	0.166	0.868123	
eu_bids	-0.0644551	0.0644278	-1.000	0.317106	
contract_lots	0.2502111	0.1207001	2.073	0.038172	*

year2022	0.4294703	0.1041624	4.123	0.0000373834	***
year2023	0.3135728	0.1061923	2.953	0.003148	**

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 4897.4 on 12553 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 4761.6 on 12543 degrees of freedom
AIC: 4783.6

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 6

Appendix H Separate Estimations by Year

Appendix Figure 11 Average Marginal Effects by Year

\$`2021`

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
    measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
    discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots, family = binomial(1
ink = "logit"),
    data = df_placeholder)
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
(Intercept)	-0.129775	0.109057	-1.190	0.234
asset_specificity	-1.364650	0.045867	-29.752	< 0.0000000000000002 ***
measurability	0.146289	0.026424	5.536	0.00000003090704 ***
political_control	0.082783	0.004712	17.569	< 0.0000000000000002 ***
framework_agreement	0.226198	0.032243	7.015	0.000000000000229 ***
discretion	0.123930	0.011181	11.084	< 0.0000000000000002 ***

```
total_bids      0.010448    0.001686    6.198      0.00000000057347 ***
eu_bids        -0.051847    0.010033   -5.168      0.00000023713492 ***
contract_lots  -0.142459    0.032972   -4.321      0.00001556255758 ***
```

```
---
```

```
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)
```

```
Null deviance: 104615 on 174122 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 103104 on 174114 degrees of freedom
AIC: 103122
```

```
Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 5
```

```
$`2022`
```

```
Call:
```

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
  measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
  discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots, family = binomial(1),
link = "logit"),
  data = df_placeholder)
```

```
Coefficients:
```

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	-0.286862	0.106289	-2.699	0.00696	**
asset_specificity	-1.237623	0.045105	-27.439	< 0.0000000000000002	***
measurability	0.113456	0.025921	4.377	0.00001202946758	***
political_control	0.058227	0.004676	12.453	< 0.0000000000000002	***
framework_agreement	0.380167	0.029250	12.997	< 0.0000000000000002	***
discretion	0.166456	0.010718	15.531	< 0.0000000000000002	***
total_bids	0.002090	0.001051	1.988	0.04679	*
eu_bids	-0.092154	0.012689	-7.262	0.000000000000038	***
contract_lots	-0.147160	0.032294	-4.557	0.00000519198386	***

```
---
```

```
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)
```

```
Null deviance: 105550 on 179029 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 104220 on 179021 degrees of freedom
AIC: 104238
```

```
Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 5
```

```
$`2023`
```

```
Call:
```

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
  measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
  discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots, family = binomial(1),
link = "logit"),
  data = df_placeholder)
```

```
Coefficients:
```

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
--	----------	------------	---------	----------

(Intercept)	-0.108528	0.098447	-1.102		0.2703	
asset_specificity	-1.090835	0.042141	-25.886	<	0.00000000000000002	***
measurability	0.051322	0.023944	2.143		0.0321	*
political_control	-0.019311	0.004103	-4.707		0.000002515517	***
framework_agreement	0.352742	0.027013	13.058	<	0.00000000000000002	***
discretion	0.245912	0.009576	25.680	<	0.00000000000000002	***
total_bids	0.004733	0.001048	4.517		0.000006257419	***
eu_bids	-0.048634	0.009399	-5.174		0.000000228625	***
contract_lots	-0.196171	0.030438	-6.445		0.000000000116	***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 117298 on 184965 degrees of freedom
 Residual deviance: 115826 on 184957 degrees of freedom
 AIC: 115844

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 5

Appendix I Separate Estimations by Organization Type

Appendix Figure 12 Average Marginal Effects by Organization Type

`$`Fed Supreme Authority``

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
  measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
  discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
  family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

coefficients: (1 not defined because of singularities)

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
(Intercept)	2.35954	0.53690	4.395	0.00001109059243521 ***
asset_specificity	-1.81150	0.23158	-7.822	0.000000000000000518 ***
measurability	-0.43442	0.12830	-3.386	0.000709 ***
political_control	NA	NA	NA	NA
framework_agreement	0.29855	0.12267	2.434	0.014943 *
discretion	0.18706	0.05272	3.548	0.000388 ***
total_bids	0.04701	0.01161	4.049	0.00005136635791503 ***
eu_bids	-0.08812	0.10497	-0.839	0.401193
contract_lots	-0.43039	0.21341	-2.017	0.043725 *
year2022	0.63741	0.10706	5.954	0.00000000261630366 ***
year2023	0.52551	0.11254	4.670	0.00000301660075333 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 4016.8 on 6749 degrees of freedom
 Residual deviance: 3833.1 on 6740 degrees of freedom
 AIC: 3853.1

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 5

\$`Fed Up/Mid/Low Authority`

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
  measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
  discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
  family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

Coefficients: (1 not defined because of singularities)

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
(Intercept)	0.45029	0.36495	1.234	0.21727
asset_specificity	-1.45204	0.15413	-9.421	< 0.000000000000000002 ***
measurability	-0.27283	0.09584	-2.847	0.00442 **
political_control	NA	NA	NA	NA
framework_agreement	0.04070	0.10067	0.404	0.68598
discretion	0.52243	0.03489	14.972	< 0.000000000000000002 ***
total_bids	0.01780	0.01058	1.682	0.09254 .
eu_bids	-0.11345	0.08094	-1.402	0.16099
contract_lots	-0.44989	0.09501	-4.735	0.00000219 ***
year2022	0.22033	0.08051	2.737	0.00621 **
year2023	0.22503	0.08403	2.678	0.00740 **

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 7625.0 on 17580 degrees of freedom
 Residual deviance: 7262.8 on 17571 degrees of freedom
 AIC: 7282.8

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 6

\$`Fed Corporation`

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
  measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
  discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
  family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

Coefficients: (1 not defined because of singularities)

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	6.463656	0.991794	6.517	0.000000000071663726	***
asset_specificity	-4.257902	0.529978	-8.034	0.000000000000000943	***
measurability	-0.173066	0.340578	-0.508	0.6113	
political_control	NA	NA	NA	NA	
framework_agreement	0.420544	0.255741	1.644	0.1001	
discretion	-0.008314	0.138108	-0.060	0.9520	
total_bids	0.046040	0.024877	1.851	0.0642	.
eu_bids	-0.033410	0.077824	-0.429	0.6677	
contract_lots	0.022665	0.359120	0.063	0.9497	
year2022	-0.608026	0.287737	-2.113	0.0346	*
year2023	-0.158138	0.328013	-0.482	0.6297	

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 769.86 on 6329 degrees of freedom
 Residual deviance: 646.32 on 6320 degrees of freedom
 AIC: 666.32

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 8

\$`Fed Institution`

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
  measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
  discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
  family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

Coefficients: (1 not defined because of singularities)

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	0.629458	0.684442	0.920	0.35775	
asset_specificity	-1.196704	0.279061	-4.288	0.00001800215432733	***
measurability	-0.167452	0.165004	-1.015	0.31018	
political_control	NA	NA	NA	NA	
framework_agreement	1.116184	0.144119	7.745	0.00000000000000957	***
discretion	-0.135846	0.068037	-1.997	0.04586	*
total_bids	-0.002797	0.013571	-0.206	0.83669	
eu_bids	-0.418997	0.162650	-2.576	0.00999	**
contract_lots	-0.298110	0.183399	-1.625	0.10406	
year2022	0.043711	0.173613	0.252	0.80121	
year2023	1.386680	0.136319	10.172	< 0.00000000000000002	***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 2596.6 on 3678 degrees of freedom
 Residual deviance: 2355.8 on 3669 degrees of freedom
 AIC: 2375.8

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 6

\$`Fed Foundation`

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
  measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
  discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
  family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

Coefficients: (1 not defined because of singularities)

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	-1.05701	0.88031	-1.201	0.22986	
asset_specificity	-1.14475	0.37186	-3.078	0.00208	**
measurability	-0.02344	0.22222	-0.105	0.91600	
political_control	NA	NA	NA	NA	
framework_agreement	-0.21148	0.25992	-0.814	0.41585	
discretion	0.51302	0.08300	6.181	0.000000000636	***
total_bids	0.05876	0.02400	2.448	0.01437	*
eu_bids	-0.47975	0.24460	-1.961	0.04984	*
contract_lots	0.56573	0.27760	2.038	0.04156	*
year2022	0.51641	0.20514	2.517	0.01182	*
year2023	0.21966	0.20474	1.073	0.28334	

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 1455.9 on 3055 degrees of freedom
 Residual deviance: 1389.4 on 3046 degrees of freedom
 AIC: 1409.4

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 6

\$`Fed Other`

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
  measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
  discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
  family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

Coefficients: (1 not defined because of singularities)

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	-0.21367	0.34515	-0.619	0.535874	
asset_specificity	-1.10335	0.15473	-7.131	0.000000000000998	***
measurability	-0.31408	0.08181	-3.839	0.000123	***
political_control	NA	NA	NA	NA	
framework_agreement	-0.23398	0.12513	-1.870	0.061485	.
discretion	0.62972	0.02993	21.042	< 0.0000000000000002	***
total_bids	-0.01170	0.01135	-1.031	0.302638	
eu_bids	0.02098	0.02604	0.806	0.420323	

contract_lots	-0.21885	0.13857	-1.579		0.114243
year2022	-0.59627	0.08641	-6.900	0.0000000000005184	***
year2023	0.23601	0.07023	3.361		0.000778 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 9495.3 on 20743 degrees of freedom
 Residual deviance: 8831.8 on 20734 degrees of freedom
 AIC: 8851.8

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 6

\$`State Supreme Authority`

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
  measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
  discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
  family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

Coefficients: (1 not defined because of singularities)

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
(Intercept)	-0.02381	0.41945	-0.057	0.95474
asset_specificity	-0.71059	0.17441	-4.074	0.0000461606 ***
measurability	-0.18396	0.09295	-1.979	0.04780 *
political_control	NA	NA	NA	NA
framework_agreement	0.42437	0.10427	4.070	0.0000470486 ***
discretion	0.04913	0.03550	1.384	0.16640
total_bids	0.08750	0.00796	10.992	< 0.0000000000000000002 ***
eu_bids	-0.16101	0.02980	-5.403	0.0000000657 ***
contract_lots	0.36825	0.13043	2.823	0.00475 **
year2022	-0.20214	0.07756	-2.606	0.00915 **
year2023	-0.22788	0.07503	-3.037	0.00239 **

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 7214.6 on 9570 degrees of freedom
 Residual deviance: 6971.4 on 9561 degrees of freedom
 AIC: 6991.4

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 5

\$`State Up/Mid/Low Authority`

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
  measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
  discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
  family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

Coefficients: (1 not defined because of singularities)

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
--	----------	------------	---------	----------

```

(Intercept)          2.473739    0.136517   18.120 < 0.000000000000000002 ***
asset_specificity    -1.895297    0.058615  -32.335 < 0.000000000000000002 ***
measurability        0.192127    0.031277    6.143   0.000000000081126 ***
political_control     NA           NA           NA           NA
framework_agreement  0.493942    0.035786   13.803 < 0.000000000000000002 ***
discretion           0.007182    0.014822    0.485   0.628
total_bids           0.026450    0.002826    9.360 < 0.000000000000000002 ***
eu_bids              -0.163519    0.014608  -11.194 < 0.000000000000000002 ***
contract_lots        -0.485414    0.044722  -10.854 < 0.000000000000000002 ***
year2022             -0.164254    0.023968   -6.853   0.0000000000000722 ***
year2023             -0.167049    0.023736   -7.038   0.0000000000000195 ***

```

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

```

Null deviance: 68165 on 69798 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 66470 on 69789 degrees of freedom
AIC: 66490

```

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 5

\$`State Corporation`

Call:

```

glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
    measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
    discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
    family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)

```

Coefficients: (1 not defined because of singularities)

```

              Estimate Std. Error z value      Pr(>|z|)
(Intercept)  -0.4690901  0.2190888  -2.141    0.032266 *
asset_specificity  -0.3992313  0.0961537  -4.152  0.000032956823915030 ***
measurability    -0.4934945  0.0604503  -8.164  0.0000000000000000325 ***
political_control      NA           NA           NA           NA
framework_agreement  0.2067756  0.0702183   2.945    0.003232 **
discretion        0.1592849  0.0217295   7.330  0.0000000000000229537 ***
total_bids        0.0004373  0.0072589   0.060    0.951963
eu_bids           -0.1253669  0.0361316  -3.470    0.000521 ***
contract_lots      0.0259947  0.0805406   0.323    0.746883
year2022          -0.0116854  0.0543960  -0.215    0.829906
year2023          0.3905942  0.0518062   7.540  0.0000000000000047167 ***

```

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

```

Null deviance: 17000 on 28791 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 16704 on 28782 degrees of freedom
AIC: 16724

```

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 5

\$`State Institution`

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
  measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
  discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
  family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

Coefficients: (1 not defined because of singularities)

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	0.459115	0.343003	1.339	0.180728	
asset_specificity	-0.621396	0.147978	-4.199	0.00002678122000	***
measurability	-0.641318	0.092188	-6.957	0.000000000000348	***
political_control	NA	NA	NA	NA	
framework_agreement	0.013313	0.084990	0.157	0.875523	
discretion	0.169984	0.035097	4.843	0.00000127758097	***
total_bids	-0.003268	0.005522	-0.592	0.553998	
eu_bids	0.020037	0.019177	1.045	0.296091	
contract_lots	0.308209	0.092050	3.348	0.000813	***
year2022	-0.102697	0.077526	-1.325	0.185277	
year2023	-0.231274	0.075527	-3.062	0.002198	**

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 8417.9 on 17207 degrees of freedom
 Residual deviance: 8249.5 on 17198 degrees of freedom
 AIC: 8269.5

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 5

\$`State Foundation`

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
  measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
  discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
  family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

Coefficients: (1 not defined because of singularities)

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	-1.06645	0.69421	-1.536	0.124488	
asset_specificity	-1.03278	0.28356	-3.642	0.000270	***
measurability	0.62693	0.18418	3.404	0.000664	***
political_control	NA	NA	NA	NA	
framework_agreement	0.34326	0.19178	1.790	0.073485	.
discretion	-0.13543	0.07895	-1.715	0.086267	.
total_bids	0.02638	0.01888	1.398	0.162193	
eu_bids	0.01274	0.07886	0.162	0.871649	
contract_lots	0.44412	0.23844	1.863	0.062515	.
year2022	-0.53842	0.13530	-3.980	0.0000690523635284	***
year2023	-1.21717	0.16058	-7.580	0.0000000000000346	***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 2127.4 on 3453 degrees of freedom

Residual deviance: 2036.5 on 3444 degrees of freedom
AIC: 2056.5

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 5

\$`State Other`

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
  measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
  discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
  family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

Coefficients: (1 not defined because of singularities)

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
(Intercept)	0.148185	0.244999	0.605	0.5453
asset_specificity	-1.427783	0.099339	-14.373	< 0.00000000000000002 ***
measurability	0.295069	0.055551	5.312	0.000000108624504888 ***
political_control	NA	NA	NA	NA
framework_agreement	0.427698	0.052745	8.109	0.0000000000000000511 ***
discretion	-0.138708	0.025591	-5.420	0.000000059528231654 ***
total_bids	0.032161	0.005006	6.424	0.000000000132586827 ***
eu_bids	-0.177977	0.024966	-7.129	0.0000000000001012056 ***
contract_lots	-0.148325	0.087736	-1.691	0.0909 .
year2022	0.554050	0.047176	11.744	< 0.00000000000000002 ***
year2023	0.813513	0.044818	18.151	< 0.00000000000000002 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 23884 on 30358 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 23073 on 30349 degrees of freedom
AIC: 23093

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 7

\$`Mun Authority`

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
  measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
  discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
  family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

Coefficients: (1 not defined because of singularities)

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
(Intercept)	-0.8832467	0.1007952	-8.763	< 0.00000000000000002 ***
asset_specificity	-1.1071323	0.0441327	-25.086	< 0.00000000000000002 ***
measurability	0.2097964	0.0247492	8.477	< 0.00000000000000002 ***
political_control	NA	NA	NA	NA
framework_agreement	0.4100453	0.0326315	12.566	< 0.00000000000000002 ***
discretion	0.3132650	0.0101847	30.758	< 0.00000000000000002 ***
total_bids	0.0016333	0.0006291	2.596	0.009420 **
eu_bids	-0.0228345	0.0082128	-2.780	0.005430 **
contract_lots	-0.1072463	0.0289228	-3.708	0.000209 ***

```

year2022      -0.0547357  0.0192670  -2.841      0.004499 **
year2023      -0.0424864  0.0190393  -2.232      0.025647 *

```

```
---
```

```
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)
```

```

Null deviance: 125869  on 229322  degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 124351  on 229313  degrees of freedom
AIC: 124371

```

```
Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 5
```

```
$`Mun Corporation`
```

```
Call:
```

```

glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
  measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
  discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
  family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)

```

```
Coefficients: (1 not defined because of singularities)
```

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	-1.541860	0.368809	-4.181	0.0000291	***
asset_specificity	0.066727	0.156944	0.425	0.670718	
measurability	-0.852188	0.085967	-9.913	< 0.000000000000000002	***
political_control	NA	NA	NA	NA	
framework_agreement	0.306730	0.103450	2.965	0.003027	**
discretion	0.422010	0.034885	12.097	< 0.000000000000000002	***
total_bids	0.009551	0.005442	1.755	0.079233	.
eu_bids	-0.179225	0.053928	-3.323	0.000889	***
contract_lots	-0.019798	0.099419	-0.199	0.842151	
year2022	0.078457	0.072759	1.078	0.280896	
year2023	0.050351	0.071182	0.707	0.479344	

```
---
```

```
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)
```

```

Null deviance: 10568  on 30081  degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 10305  on 30072  degrees of freedom
AIC: 10325

```

```
Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 6
```

```
$`Mun Institution`
```

```
Call:
```

```

glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
  measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
  discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
  family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)

```

```
Coefficients: (1 not defined because of singularities)
```

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	-2.32076	0.57375	-4.045	0.000052347859	***

asset_specificity	-0.34120	0.25031	-1.363	0.17284	
measurability	0.09504	0.14253	0.667	0.50488	
political_control	NA	NA	NA	NA	
framework_agreement	0.06690	0.15638	0.428	0.66880	
discretion	0.32068	0.04969	6.454	0.000000000109	***
total_bids	0.00258	0.01355	0.190	0.84898	
eu_bids	-0.41538	0.13285	-3.127	0.00177	**
contract_lots	0.14097	0.17926	0.786	0.43163	
year2022	0.31323	0.12273	2.552	0.01070	*
year2023	0.46330	0.11738	3.947	0.000079143399	***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 3225.9 on 4746 degrees of freedom
 Residual deviance: 3148.6 on 4737 degrees of freedom
 AIC: 3168.6

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 6

\$`Mun Foundation`

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
  measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
  discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
  family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

Coefficients: (1 not defined because of singularities)

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	-6.74380	3.24681	-2.077	0.0378	*
asset_specificity	2.06952	1.36096	1.521	0.1284	
measurability	-0.63929	0.71184	-0.898	0.3691	
political_control	NA	NA	NA	NA	
framework_agreement	-14.85074	1136.24450	-0.013	0.9896	
discretion	0.47063	0.25397	1.853	0.0639	.
total_bids	-0.14023	0.13024	-1.077	0.2816	
eu_bids	-0.15713	0.28059	-0.560	0.5755	
contract_lots	1.29940	0.80707	1.610	0.1074	
year2022	0.08463	0.77091	0.110	0.9126	
year2023	1.55490	0.71041	2.189	0.0286	*

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 146.18 on 336 degrees of freedom
 Residual deviance: 117.92 on 327 degrees of freedom
 AIC: 137.92

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 16

\$`Mun Other`

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
  measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
  discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
  family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

Coefficients: (1 not defined because of singularities)

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	-0.57275	0.56750	-1.009	0.31286	
asset_specificity	-1.07286	0.24467	-4.385	0.00001160708898012	***
measurability	-0.40177	0.14435	-2.783	0.00538	**
political_control	NA	NA	NA	NA	
framework_agreement	-0.19976	0.17834	-1.120	0.26268	
discretion	0.40007	0.05004	7.995	0.000000000000000129	***
total_bids	0.02271	0.01227	1.850	0.06424	.
eu_bids	-0.03315	0.04728	-0.701	0.48325	
contract_lots	0.08539	0.17224	0.496	0.62008	
year2022	0.28781	0.13135	2.191	0.02844	*
year2023	0.28368	0.12783	2.219	0.02648	*

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 4038.3 on 13868 degrees of freedom
 Residual deviance: 3939.8 on 13859 degrees of freedom
 AIC: 3959.8

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 6

\$`Remaining Other`

Call:

```
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
  measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
  discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + year,
  family = binomial(link = "logit"), data = df_placeholder)
```

Coefficients: (1 not defined because of singularities)

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	-0.716048	0.228424	-3.135	0.00172	**
asset_specificity	-0.550709	0.097693	-5.637	0.00000001729009335	***
measurability	-0.458283	0.058916	-7.779	0.000000000000000733	***
political_control	NA	NA	NA	NA	
framework_agreement	0.143130	0.059934	2.388	0.01693	*
discretion	0.215158	0.021533	9.992	< 0.000000000000000002	***
total_bids	0.005609	0.005625	0.997	0.31865	
eu_bids	-0.043060	0.021440	-2.008	0.04460	*
contract_lots	0.367979	0.065461	5.621	0.00000001895058712	***
year2022	-0.188250	0.054250	-3.470	0.00052	***
year2023	0.560700	0.047367	11.837	< 0.000000000000000002	***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 19263 on 42437 degrees of freedom
 Residual deviance: 18708 on 42428 degrees of freedom

AIC: 18728

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 6

Appendix J Adding Contract Value Covariate

Beware that contract value is on a very different scale than the other variables. Next to its inclusion in the model not being justified theoretically, this is the main technical reason not to include it.

```
> margineffects::avg_slopes(m3_state_contract_value)
```

Term	Contrast	Estimate	Std. Error	z	Pr(> z)	S	2.5 %	97.5 %
asset_specificity	dY/dX	-0.092630593	0.01355015490	-6.84	<0.001	36.8	-0.1191884090	-0.0660727779
contract_lots	1 - 0	-0.005648975	0.00164189809	-3.44	<0.001	10.8	-0.0088670357	-0.0024309135
contract_value	dY/dX	-0.000000066	0.00000000978	-6.75	<0.001	36.0	-0.0000000852	-0.0000000468
discretion	dY/dX	0.016446052	0.00242730835	6.78	<0.001	36.2	0.0116886156	0.0212034894
eu_bids	dY/dX	-0.004366928	0.00079517530	-5.49	<0.001	24.6	-0.0059254426	-0.0028084127
framework_agreement	1 - 0	0.018650769	0.00307039615	6.07	<0.001	29.6	0.0126329027	0.0246686344
measurability	dY/dX	0.005817239	0.00144187611	4.03	<0.001	14.2	0.0029912135	0.0086432640
political_control	dY/dX	0.005960557	0.00088938080	6.70	<0.001	35.5	0.0042174026	0.0077037113
total_bids	dY/dX	0.000470749	0.00009256380	5.09	<0.001	21.4	0.0002893269	0.0006521704
year	2022 - 2021	-0.002413583	0.00099700904	-2.42	0.0155	6.0	-0.0043676847	-0.0004594811
year	2023 - 2021	0.007666897	0.00145367190	5.27	<0.001	22.8	0.0048177528	0.0105160419

Type: response

```
> summary(m3_state_contract_value)
```

```
Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Adaptive Gauss-Hermite Quadrature, nAGQ = 0) ['glmerMod']
Family: binomial ( logit )
Formula: environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity + measurability + framework_agreement + political_co
ntrol + discretion + total_bids +
eu_bids + contract_lots + (1 | federal_state) + year + contract_value
Data: df_imp_15
```

Control: glmerControl(optimizer = "bobyqa")

AIC	BIC	logLik	deviance	df.resid
306908.2	307053.7	-153441.1	306882.2	538106

Scaled residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-578.91	-0.34	-0.27	-0.20	17.98

Random effects:

Groups	Name	Variance	Std.Dev.
federal_state	(Intercept)	0.5885	0.7671

Number of obs: 538119, groups: federal_state, 16

Fixed effects:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	-0.62900278478	0.20163969522	-3.119	0.001812	**
asset_specificity	-1.17257638360	0.02598495851	-45.125	< 0.0000000000000002	***
measurability	0.07363827188	0.01481508076	4.970	0.000000667824848218	***
framework_agreement	0.22018973159	0.01740351789	12.652	< 0.0000000000000002	***
political_control	0.07545248341	0.00276270879	27.311	< 0.0000000000000002	***
discretion	0.20818448908	0.00616109423	33.790	< 0.0000000000000002	***
total_bids	0.00595903242	0.00079409647	7.504	0.0000000000000061821	***
eu_bids	-0.05527931889	0.00612527295	-9.025	< 0.0000000000000002	***
contract_lots	-0.07318931122	0.01884332703	-3.884	0.000103	***
year2022	-0.03146011351	0.01215536627	-2.588	0.009649	**
year2023	0.09525791548	0.01179503887	8.076	0.000000000000000669	***
contract_value	-0.00000083562	0.00000002702	-30.922	< 0.0000000000000002	***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Correlation of Fixed Effects:

	(Intr)	asst_s	msrblt	frmwr_	pltcl_	dscrtn	ttl_bd	eu_bds	cntrct_l	yr2022	yr2023
asst_spcfct	-0.221										
measurablt	-0.095	-0.370									
frmwrk_grmn	-0.008	-0.071	0.117								
pltcl_cntrl	-0.078	0.064	-0.027	0.048							

```
discretion -0.009 -0.108 -0.017 -0.075 0.086
total_bids -0.022 0.037 0.012 0.009 -0.051 0.008
eu_bids -0.007 0.017 -0.001 0.005 0.026 -0.022 -0.057
contrct_lts -0.028 0.006 0.133 -0.071 -0.019 -0.083 -0.109 -0.029
year2022 -0.031 0.003 0.002 -0.014 -0.004 -0.003 0.025 0.004 -0.001
year2023 -0.031 0.000 0.001 -0.010 0.004 -0.002 0.010 0.002 -0.002 0.517
contract_vl 0.002 -0.035 -0.019 -0.074 0.016 -0.085 -0.079 -0.047 -0.090 -0.021 -0.027
```

fit warnings:

Some predictor variables are on very different scales: consider rescaling

Appendix K Adding Product Type Covariate

AMEs

Term	Contrast	Estimate	Std. Error	z	Pr(> z)	S	CI2.5 %	CI97.5 %
asset_specificity	dY/dX	-0.073804	0.0109051	-6.77	< 0.001	36.2	-0.0951781	-0.052431
contract_lots	1 - 0	-0.002129	0.0014959	-1.42	0.15466	2.7	-0.0050609	0.000803
discretion	dY/dX	0.026605	0.0038933	6.83	< 0.001	36.8	0.0189740	0.034236
eu_bids	dY/dX	-0.005396	0.0009209	-5.86	< 0.001	27.7	-0.0072008	-0.003591
framework_agreement	1 - 0	0.022592	0.0035717	6.33	< 0.001	31.9	0.0155915	0.029592
measurability	dY/dX	-0.005157	0.0014778	-3.49	< 0.001	11.0	-0.0080532	-0.002260
political_control	dY/dX	0.004887	0.0007413	6.59	< 0.001	34.4	0.0034339	0.006340
product_type	Social specific service	-0.113792	0.0184647	-6.16	< 0.001	30.4	-0.1499827	-0.077602
product_type	Service contract	-0.048093	0.0070777	-6.80	< 0.001	36.4	-0.0619654	-0.034221
product_type	Supply contract	-0.038909	0.0056872	-6.84	< 0.001	36.9	-0.0500555	-0.027762
total_bids	dY/dX	0.000172	0.0000544	3.17	0.00153	9.4	0.0000658	0.000279
year	2022 - 2021	-0.002687	0.0010109	-2.66	0.00787	7.0	-0.0046680	-0.000705
year	2023 - 2021	0.007436	0.0014294	5.20	< 0.001	22.3	0.0046349	0.010238

Type: response

> [summary\(m3_state_product_type\)](#)

Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Adaptive Gauss-Hermite Quadrature, nAGQ = 0) ['glmerMod']

Family: binomial (logit)

Formula: environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity + measurability + framework_agreement + political_control + discretion + total_bids +

eu_bids + contract_lots + (1 | federal_state) + year + product_type

Data: df_imp_15

Control: glmerControl(optimizer = "bobyqa")

AIC	BIC	logLik	deviance	df.resid
305483.7	305651.6	-152726.9	305453.7	538104

Scaled residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-4.5880	-0.3485	-0.2630	-0.1993	28.3143

Random effects:

Groups	Name	Variance	Std.Dev.
federal_state	(Intercept)	0.5979	0.7732

Number of obs: 538119, groups: federal_state, 16

Fixed effects:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	-0.7579099	0.2052876	-3.692	0.000223	***
asset_specificity	-0.9371180	0.0271177	-34.557	< 0.0000000000000002	***
measurability	-0.0654764	0.0161937	-4.043	0.00005269807176789	***
framework_agreement	0.2639281	0.0175459	15.042	< 0.0000000000000002	***
political_control	0.0620490	0.0027701	22.399	< 0.0000000000000002	***
discretion	0.3378094	0.0069546	48.574	< 0.0000000000000002	***
total_bids	0.0021893	0.0006138	3.567	0.000361	***
eu_bids	-0.0685139	0.0061878	-11.072	< 0.0000000000000002	***
contract_lots	-0.0272672	0.0189060	-1.442	0.149231	
year2022	-0.0351131	0.0121712	-2.885	0.003915	**
year2023	0.0926355	0.0118108	7.843	0.00000000000000439	***
product_typeSupply contract	-0.4802117	0.0142637	-33.667	< 0.0000000000000002	***
product_typeService contract	-0.6249657	0.0143735	-43.480	< 0.0000000000000002	***
product_typeContracts for social or other specific services	-5.2067129	1.0011259	-5.201	0.00000019837144771	***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Appendix L Complete Case Analysis

The analyses are replicated on the dataframe containing all model variables after listwise deletion.

Logistic General Linear Model

```
Call:
glm(formula = environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity +
     measurability + political_control + framework_agreement +
     discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots, family = binomial(link = "logit"),
     data = df_listwise)
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
(Intercept)	-0.095858	0.094805	-1.011	0.312
asset_specificity	-1.033085	0.040553	-25.475	< 2e-16 ***
measurability	-0.092689	0.023150	-4.004	6.23e-05 ***
political_control	0.005577	0.003964	1.407	0.159
framework_agreement	0.160193	0.027878	5.746	9.13e-09 ***
discretion	0.193509	0.009174	21.092	< 2e-16 ***
total_bids	0.004768	0.001224	3.896	9.79e-05 ***
eu_bids	-0.072568	0.009392	-7.727	1.10e-14 ***
contract_lots	-0.030862	0.026880	-1.148	0.251

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 128519 on 231982 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 127249 on 231974 degrees of freedom
AIC: 127267

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 5

```
>
>
> AIC(model_listwise)
[1] 127266.6
> BIC(model_listwise)
[1] 127359.8
```

```
> marginaleffects::avg_slopes(model_listwise)
```

	Term Contrast	Estimate	Std. Error	z	Pr(> z)	S
2.5 %						
97.5 %						
asset_specificity	dy/dx	-0.074968	2.96e-03	-25.29	<0.001	466.5 -
0.080777						
-0.069159						
contract_lots	1 - 0	-0.002216	1.91e-03	-1.16	0.246	2.0 -
0.005961						
0.001528						
discretion	dy/dx	0.014042	6.69e-04	20.99	<0.001	322.6
0.012731						
0.015354						

eu_bids	dY/dX	-0.005266	6.82e-04	-7.72	<0.001	46.3	-
0.006603 -0.003929							
framework_agreement	1 - 0	0.012296	2.26e-03	5.44	<0.001	24.2	
0.007866 0.016725							
measurability	dY/dX	-0.006726	1.68e-03	-4.00	<0.001	14.0	-
0.010019 -0.003433							
political_control	dY/dX	0.000405	2.87e-04	1.41	0.158	2.7	-
0.000157 0.000967							
total_bids	dY/dX	0.000346	8.88e-05	3.90	<0.001	13.3	
0.000172 0.000520							

Type: response

Logistic General Linear Mixed Model with Random Intercept per State

Generalized linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood (Adaptive Gauss-Hermite Quadrature, nAGQ = 0) ['glmerMod']

Family: binomial (logit)

Formula: environmental_sustainability ~ asset_specificity + measurability + political_control + framework_agreement + discretion + total_bids + eu_bids + contract_lots + (1 | federal_state)

Data: df_listwise

Control: glmerControl(optimizer = "bobyqa")

AIC	BIC	logLik	deviance	df.resid
125203.3	125306.8	-62591.6	125183.3	231973

Scaled residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-2.662	-0.324	-0.285	-0.223	39.822

Random effects:

Groups	Name	Variance	Std.Dev.
federal_state	(Intercept)	0.3348	0.5786

Number of obs: 231983, groups: federal_state, 16

Fixed effects:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
(Intercept)	-0.337180	0.173917	-1.939	0.052534 .
asset_specificity	-1.029513	0.040558	-25.384	< 2e-16 ***
measurability	-0.115833	0.023176	-4.998	5.79e-07 ***
political_control	0.021680	0.004094	5.295	1.19e-07 ***
framework_agreement	0.112000	0.028204	3.971	7.16e-05 ***
discretion	0.170692	0.009324	18.307	< 2e-16 ***
total_bids	0.004710	0.001245	3.782	0.000156 ***
eu_bids	-0.084214	0.009719	-8.665	< 2e-16 ***
contract_lots	0.007949	0.027063	0.294	0.768961

 Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Correlation of Fixed Effects:

	(Intr)	asst_s	msrblt	plctl_	frmwr_	dscrtn	ttl_bd	eu_bds
asst_spcfct	-0.397							
measurablty	-0.173	-0.373						
plctl_cntrl	-0.141	0.061	-0.003					
frmwrk_grmn	-0.010	-0.080	0.112	0.055				

```

discretion -0.020 -0.126 0.004 0.116 -0.088
total_bids -0.037 0.031 -0.003 -0.037 -0.001 0.010
eu_bids -0.009 0.005 0.001 0.039 0.004 -0.036 -0.059
contrct_lts -0.046 0.003 0.120 -0.035 -0.092 -0.106 -0.127 -0.026

```

```
> marginaleffects::avg_slopes(m_state_CCA)
```

	Term	Contrast	Estimate	Std. Error	z	Pr(> z)	S
2.5 %							
97.5 %							
	asset_specificity	dY/dX	-0.074049	9.29e-03	-7.967	<0.001	49.1 -0
	.092265						
	-0.055834						
	contract_lots	1 - 0	0.000573	1.96e-03	0.293	0.77	0.4 -0
	.003264						
	0.004411						
	discretion	dY/dX	0.012277	1.61e-03	7.625	<0.001	45.2 0
	.009122						
	0.015433						
	eu_bids	dY/dX	-0.006057	1.00e-03	-6.033	<0.001	29.2 -0
	.008025						
	-0.004090						
	framework_agreement	1 - 0	0.008371	2.40e-03	3.486	<0.001	11.0 0
	.003665						
	0.013076						
	measurability	dY/dX	-0.008331	1.94e-03	-4.297	<0.001	15.8 -0
	.012132						
	-0.004531						
	political_control	dY/dX	0.001559	3.49e-04	4.472	<0.001	17.0 0
	.000876						
	0.002243						
	total_bids	dY/dX	0.000339	9.82e-05	3.448	<0.001	10.8 0
	.000146						
	0.000531						

```
Type: response
```

Appendix M Pooled Marginal Effects to Account for Imputation-Related Uncertainty

Pooled across 50 imputed datasets.

Appendix Table 4 Pooled Marginal Effects Across 50 Imputed Datasets

Variable	AME	Std Error	Df	p-value	CI 2.5%	CI 97.5%
(Intercept)	-0.17205	0.062761	9630.475	6.13E-03	-0.29508	-0.04903
asset_specificity	-1.2439	0.026647	7348.168	0.00E+00	-1.29613	-1.19166
measurability	0.113549	0.015329	6234.498	1.46E-13	0.083499	0.143599
political_control	0.036246	0.00261	45743.56	9.07E-44	0.031131	0.041361
framework_agreement	0.342569	0.022665	240.4821	9.82E-37	0.297921	0.387216
discretion	0.186561	0.007548	356.7555	2.67E-79	0.171716	0.201406
total_bids	0.004734	0.001106	163.9174	3.18E-05	0.00255	0.006918
eu_bids	-0.05277	0.008587	173.5193	5.32E-09	-0.06972	-0.03582
contract_lots	-0.14837	0.020022	1713.621	1.97E-13	-0.18764	-0.10909
year2022	-0.03842	0.012118	46163.48	1.52E-03	-0.06217	-0.01467
year2023	0.079975	0.011739	47853.89	9.70E-12	0.056966	0.102985

Appendix N Validation of Regression-Based Model with Random Forest-Based Model

Random forest models are more robust against imbalanced outcomes than logistic regression models. The random forest builds 500 trees and only includes focal variables (less noise). This model indicates that more complex and probably non-linear relationships undergird the propensity to contract for environmental outcomes (Appendix O). While the model accuracy is high (91.8% correct predictions), the no information rate (always predicting no environmental criteria) is equally high at 90.9%. Only 16.91% of actual cases where environmental criteria are used, are correctly identified (very low specificity). However, when the model does predict that environmental criteria are used, it is correct 70.55% of the time.

As Appendix Table 5, which is sorted descendingly by the mean decrease accuracy of the focal variables, shows, omitting the political control structure and location (federal state) of the buyer organization would drastically reduce the predictive accuracy of the random forest model. This indicates that there may be non-linear interactions between the focal variables, indicating a need for a theory of hollow states that captures more complexity across levels of government. The error plot shows that the model performance barely improves over trees.

Appendix Table 5 Mean Decrease Accuracy and Mean Decrease Gini

Focal variable	Outcome=0	Outcome=1	MeanDecreaseAccuracy	MeanDecreaseGini
political_control	172.00017	241.3931	302.61389	3899.6901
federal_state	148.74747	323.245	282.82795	5673.8839
discretion	146.37325	59.00042	171.33945	737.0458
asset_specificity	118.26754	103.295	141.58596	3489.3108
measurability	108.31818	96.80631	133.60675	3509.2013
total_bids	115.32206	44.18325	130.86758	2809.5548
year	61.70939	94.9172	101.91656	1408.449
contract_lots	79.06044	51.55927	101.83779	585.4498
framework_agreement	74.71713	33.11246	85.97641	488.9012
eu_bids	34.09017	20.5832	41.20109	723.0126

```
> confusionMatrix(p1, train$environmental_sustainability)
Confusion Matrix and Statistics
```

	Reference	
Prediction	0	1
0	340690	24870
1	1885	9301

```
Accuracy : 0.929
95% CI : (0.9282, 0.9298)
No Information Rate : 0.9093
P-Value [Acc > NIR] : < 0.000000000000000022
```

```
Kappa : 0.3825
```

```
McNemar's Test P-value : < 0.000000000000000022
```

```
Sensitivity : 0.9945
Specificity : 0.2722
Pos Pred Value : 0.9320
Neg Pred Value : 0.8315
Prevalence : 0.9093
Detection Rate : 0.9043
Detection Prevalence : 0.9703
Balanced Accuracy : 0.6333
```

```
'Positive' Class : 0
```

```
>
> p2 <- predict(rf, test)
> confusionMatrix(p2, test$environmental_sustainability)
Confusion Matrix and Statistics
```

	Reference	
Prediction	0	1
0	145649	12203
1	1037	2484

```
Accuracy : 0.918
95% CI : (0.9166, 0.9193)
No Information Rate : 0.909
P-Value [Acc > NIR] : < 0.000000000000000022
```

```
Kappa : 0.2463
```

```
McNemar's Test P-value : < 0.000000000000000022
```

```
Sensitivity : 0.9929
Specificity : 0.1691
Pos Pred Value : 0.9227
Neg Pred Value : 0.7055
Prevalence : 0.9090
Detection Rate : 0.9026
Detection Prevalence : 0.9782
Balanced Accuracy : 0.5810
```

```
'Positive' Class : 0
```

Appendix Figure 13 Partial Dependence Plots

Appendix Figure 14 Top 10 by Importance of Focal Variable

An alternative random forest model with equal sampling from each outcome class did not improve overall performance, while improving specificity. Due to less overfitting to outcome class 0, it showed smoother partial dependence curves for asset specificity and measurability, which approximate a linear relationship that the logit GLMM (the main model in the article assumed). The error plot below shows that this model learns non-obvious patterns, since the error lines change up until 200 trees, whereas the error plot of the original model did not show learning. The mean accuracy decrease is highest when removing political control from the random forest computation. The partial dependence plot for political control indicates that this mainly driven by public sector organizations with rank 5 political control. Namely, entities that are headed by unelected officials who are always overseen by an entity with an elected government head. They are upper, middle and lower authorities at the federal and state level.

Appendix Figure 15 Random Forest Error Rate by Trees

Appendix Figure 16 Top 10 by Importance of Focal Variable

Confusion Matrix and Statistics

		Reference	
		0	1
Prediction	0	244959	16903
	1	97616	17268

Accuracy : 0.696
 95% CI : (0.6946, 0.6975)
 No Information Rate : 0.9093
 P-Value [Acc > NIR] : 1

Kappa : 0.1068

Mcnemar's Test P-value : <0.0000000000000002

Sensitivity : 0.7151
 Specificity : 0.5053
 Pos Pred Value : 0.9355
 Neg Pred Value : 0.1503
 Prevalence : 0.9093
 Detection Rate : 0.6502
 Detection Prevalence : 0.6951
 Balanced Accuracy : 0.6102

'Positive' Class : 0

```
>
> p2 <- predict(rf, test)
> confusionMatrix(p2, test$environmental_sustainability)
Confusion Matrix and Statistics
```

```

                Reference
Prediction      0      1
0 104977      7281
1  41709      7406

                Accuracy : 0.6964
                95% CI : (0.6942, 0.6987)
No Information Rate : 0.909
P-Value [Acc > NIR] : 1

                Kappa : 0.107

McNemar's Test P-value : <0.0000000000000002

                Sensitivity : 0.7157
                Specificity : 0.5043
                Pos Pred Value : 0.9351
                Neg Pred Value : 0.1508
                Prevalence : 0.9090
                Detection Rate : 0.6505
                Detection Prevalence : 0.6956
                Balanced Accuracy : 0.6100

                'Positive' Class : 0

```

```

>
> plot(rf)
>
> # tune model
> t <- tuneRF(train[,-1], train[,1],
+           stepFactor = 0.5,
+           plot = TRUE,
+           ntreeTry = 150,
+           trace = TRUE,
+           improve = 0.05)
mtry = 2  OOB error = 9.07%
Searching left ...
mtry = 4  OOB error = 9.21%
-0.01545984 0.05
Searching right ...
mtry = 1  OOB error = 9.07%
-0.0005270401 0.05
>
> hist(treesize(rf),
+      main = "No. of Nodes for the Trees",
+      col = "green")
>
> ##Variable Importance
> varImpPlot(rf,
+           sort = T,
+           n.var = 8,
+           main = "Top 10 - Variable Importance")
> importance(rf)

```

	0	1	MeanDecreaseAccuracy	MeanDecreaseGini
asset_specificity	1.1347499	14.633171	3.149133	12.369193
measurability	0.7448573	10.533898	2.185941	12.119478
framework_agreement	4.1489381	5.101586	4.878531	1.996465
political_control	9.2375180	27.397502	14.405077	8.004024

discretion	4.6104913	9.277025	5.925946	3.346871
total_bids	1.9035739	4.792132	2.765247	10.162618
eu_bids	3.9004928	5.003035	5.062507	2.530981
contract_lots	4.7113128	1.516142	5.439310	1.736109

>

Appendix Figure 17 Partial dependence plots

Appendix References

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